

The positive allosteric modulator of $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptors, 3-furan-2-yl-N-p-tolyl-acrylamide, enhances memory processes and stimulates ERK1/2 phosphorylation in mice

Authors Manuscript

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Highlights

- PAM-2 improves memory processes after acute and chronic treatments.
- The promnesic activity of PAM-2 is inhibited by methyllycaconitine, indicating that the process is mediated by $\alpha 7$ nAChRs.
- Inactive doses of PAM-2 and DMXBA, but not nicotine, improve memory in a synergistic manner.
- PAM-2 reverses scopolamine-induced memory deficits.
- The chronic, but not acute, treatment with PAM-2 increases ERK1/2 kinase phosphorylation in hippocampus and prefrontal cortex.

Abbreviations

5-HT, 5-hydroxytryptamine (serotonin); CNS, central nervous system; PFC, prefrontal cortex; Ach, acetylcholine; AD, Alzheimer's disease; DMXBA (GTS-21), (2,4)-dimethoxybenzylidene anabaseine dihydrochloride; nAChR, nicotinic acetylcholine receptor; ERK1/2, extracellular signal-regulated protein kinase 1/2; LTM, long-term memory; LTP, long-term potentiation; MLA, methyllycaconitine; PA, passive avoidance; PAM-2, 3-furan-2-yl-N-p-tolyl-acrylamide; i.p., intraperitoneal; s.c., subcutaneous; PMSF, phenylmethanesulfonyl fluoride.

Keywords

$\alpha 7$ Nicotinic acetylcholine receptor, $\alpha 7$ Up-regulation, Positive allosteric modulator, Memory, passive avoidance, Nicotine, DMXBA, ERK1/2 phosphorylation

Abstract

To determine whether 3-furan-2-yl-N-p-tolyl-acrylamide (PAM-2), a positive allosteric modulator of $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs), improves memory processes, passive avoidance tests were conducted in male mice after acute and chronic treatments. To determine the neuronal mechanisms underlying the promnesic activity elicited by PAM-2, the effect of this ligand on $\alpha 7$ nAChR up-regulation and ERK1/2 phosphorylation was assessed in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex. The results indicate that: (1) PAM-2 improves memory acquisition/consolidation after acute treatment (Day 2) and memory consolidation after chronic treatment (Day 22). Although no effect was observed on $\alpha 7$ nAChR up-regulation, the chronic, but not acute, PAM-2 treatment increases ERK1/2 kinase phosphorylation, (2) the promnesic activity of PAM-2 was inhibited by methyllycaconitine, a selective $\alpha 7$ -antagonist, confirming the role of $\alpha 7$ nAChRs, (3) a synergistic (acute) effect was observed between inactive doses of PAM-2 (0.1 mg/kg) and DMXBA (0.3 mg/kg), a selective $\alpha 7$ -agonist, and (4) PAM-2 reversed the memory impairment elicited by scopolamine, a muscarinic antagonist. The results demonstrate that PAM-2 presents promnesic activity mediated by $\alpha 7$ nAChRs, and is able to trigger ERK1/2 phosphorylation only after chronic treatment.

Disclaimer

This is a slightly polished and reformatted version of the following manuscript: Targowska-Duda KM, Wnorowski A, Budzynska B, Jozwiak K, Biala G, Arias HR. *The positive allosteric modulator of $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptors, 3-furan-2-yl-N-p-tolyl-acrylamide, enhances memory processes and stimulates ERK1/2 phosphorylation in mice*, which has been published in final form at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbr.2016.01.002> (Behav Brain Res. 2016 Apr 1;302:142-51. doi: 10.1016/j.bbr.2016.01.002. Epub 2016 Jan 8).

1 Introduction

The $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) is considered a potential target for novel psychopharmacological treatments for neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's (AD) and Parkinson's diseases as well as schizophrenia (reviewed in Ref. [1]). Several brain regions showing $\alpha 7$ nAChR expression (e.g., hippocampus, thalamus, midbrain, and cortex) are also associated with the cognitive deficits seen in schizophrenics and AD patients (reviewed in Ref. [2]).

Agonists of $\alpha 7$ nAChRs are currently being developed for the treatment of memory impairments in patients with schizophrenia and AD (reviewed in Ref. [3]). Selective $\alpha 7$ agonists enhance cognitive performance, possibly involving changes in hippocampal synaptic plasticity [4]. For instance, long-term treatment with nicotinic agonists up-regulates $\alpha 7$ nAChRs, supporting the idea that this mechanism may underlie the sustained procognitive effects elicited by selective $\alpha 7$ agonists (reviewed in Ref. [5]). Nevertheless, the chronic administration of selective agonists may provide not only $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation, but also subsequent desensitization, producing side effects. In this regard, an alternative approach to increase $\alpha 7$ nAChR function can be used by means of selective type II positive allosteric modulators (PAMs) of $\alpha 7$ nAChR. Type II PAMs enhance the activity of the endogenous neurotransmitters ACh and choline, without inducing desensitization (reviewed in Ref. [6,7]).

Several groups are studying $\alpha 7$ -selective PAMs at various preclinical and clinical stages (reviewed in Ref. [3]). 3-Furan-2-yl-N-p-tolylacrylamide (PAM-2), an $\alpha 7$ -selective PAM [8], reactivates desensitized $\alpha 7$ nAChRs, resembling the properties of type II PAMs [9]. Interestingly, this novel PAM produces antidepressant-like activity [9,10] as well as antinociceptive and anti-inflammatory activity in mice [11]. PAM-2, as well as other $\alpha 7$ -PAMs (reviewed in Refs. [5,6,8]), has procognitive activity [12]. However, there is no experimental evidence of the beneficial effects of PAMs after chronic treatments, and the intracellular signaling pathways triggered in neuronal cells in response to PAMs are not clearly understood. In this regard, we want to evaluate whether PAM-2 improves memory processes by using the passive avoidance (PA) test in male mice, and compare, for the first time, between acute and chronic treatments with PAM-2. To determine whether the PAM-2 activity is mediated by $\alpha 7$ nAChRs, and the neuronal mechanisms involved in this process, a series of experiments were performed to demonstrate (1) the effect of methyllycaconitine (MLA) (an $\alpha 7$ -selective antagonist) on the observed PAM-2 activity, (2) the potential synergistic interaction between nAChR agonists and PAM-2, and (3) how acute and chronic treatments with PAM-2 affect $\alpha 7$ nAChR expression as well as extracellular signal-regulated protein kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) phosphorylation in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex (PFC). Previous results indicated that $\alpha 7$ -selective PAMs, contrary to agonists, do not induce $\alpha 7$ nAChR up-regulation in different brain areas [13]. Our study will corroborate the initial studies performed with type I and II PAMs. Finally, (4) the favorable effect of PAM-2 in decreasing the memory impairment elicited by the muscarinic antagonist scopolamine (e.g., see [12]) was also determined.

The activation of the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) signaling cascade, in particular ERK1/2 phosphorylation, plays an important role in the formation of long-term memory (LTM), especially in the hippocampus [14] and PFC [15]. For example, $\alpha 7$ nAChR agonists increase ERK1/2 phosphorylation in the PFC and hippocampus [4,15], and ERK1/2 is activated in the PFC after learning activity [16]. Studies on PC12 cells also indicate that the selective agonist PNU-282987 in the presence of PNU-120596, a type II $\alpha 7$ -PAM, increases ERK1/2 phosphorylation [17]. Our results indicate that PAM-2 presents procognitive activity mediated by $\alpha 7$ nAChRs, and that the chronic treatment stimulates the ERK1/2 phosphorylation in hippocampus and PFC in mice.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Drugs

(-)-Nicotine hydrogen tartrate, scopolamine hydrobromide, (2.4)-dimethoxybenzylidene anabaseine dihydrochloride (DMXBA, also called GTS-21), sodium orthovanadate, protease inhibitor cocktail, Tween 20, Tween 80, were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Sodium chloride (NaCl) was purchased from Baxter (Lublin, Poland). Methyllycaconitine (MLA), and antibodies for the $\alpha 7$ nAChR (#ab23832) and β -actin were obtained from Abcam (Cambridge, UK). Antibodies detecting phospho-ERK1/2 (#4376, Thr202/Tyr204) and total ERK1/2 (#4695) were purchased from Cell Signaling Technology (Danvers, MA, USA). EDTA and EGTA were purchased from Boston BioProducts (Ashland, MA, USA). Phenylmethanesulfonyl fluoride (PMSF) was obtained from Santa Cruz Biotechnology (Dallas, TX, USA). Phosphatase inhibitor cocktail sets I and II were purchased from Calbiochem (San Diego, CA, USA). The bicinchoninic acid assay kit was obtained from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membranes and 4–12% pre cast polyacrylamide gels were purchased from Invitrogen (Carlsbad, CA, USA). Horseshoe peroxidase-conjugated secondary antibodies were obtained from Santa Cruz Biotechnology (Santa Cruz, CA, USA), and the Cell Lysis Buffer was obtained from Cell Signaling Technology (MA, USA). PAM-2 was synthesized as described in Arias et al [8].

2.2 Animals

The experiments were carried out on naïve male Swiss mice (Farm of Laboratory Animals, Warszawa, Poland), two months old, weighing 20–30 g. The experiments were carried out according to the National Institute of Health Guidelines for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals and the European Community Council Directive for Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (2010/63/EU) and approved by local ethics committee (license N° 45/2012, N° 53/2013, and N° 43/2015). The animals were maintained under standard laboratory conditions (12-h light/dark cycle; room temperature 21 ± 1 °C; 40–50% humidity) with free access to tap water and laboratory chow (Agropol, Poland) in their home cages and were adapted to the laboratory conditions for at least one week before the experiments.

2.3 Passive avoidance task

To test the activity of PAM-2 on memory processes, the PA task, a fear-motivated test classically used to assess memory processes [18], was used. The apparatus consists of two compartments, one illuminated with fluorescent light (8 W) (10 × 13 × 15 cm) and another darkened (25 × 20 × 15 cm), connected by a guillotine door. Both chambers had an electric grid floor. The experimental procedure involves examination of different memory stages, according to the drug treatment time, and includes formation of memory traces, and memory consolidation (i.e., stabilization of a memory trace). For memory acquisition/consolidation, the animals received the substance(s) before the test, whereas in the case of memory consolidation the animals received the injection(s) after the test.

The test was performed in two steps: on the first day (i.e., Day 1), mice were placed individually into the illuminated compartment and allowed to explore it for 30 s. After that, the door is raised to allow the mouse to enter into the dark compartment. The maximum time for exploring both compartments when the door is open is 300 s. When the mouse enters into the dark compartment, the door is automatically closed and an electric foot-shock (0.15 mA) of 2-s duration is immediately delivered to the animal via the grid floor, the training latency time (i.e., TL1) for entering the dark compartment is recorded, and the mouse is subsequently removed from the dark compartment. If the mouse fails to enter into the dark box within 300 s, it is excluded from further tests. After 24 h (i.e., Day 2), each mouse is placed again in the illuminated compartment to determine the retention latency time (i.e., TL2). In this regard, after 30 s of adaptation period in the illuminated chamber, the door is raised and the time to reenter to the dark compartment is recorded, although in this case no foot-shock is applied. Our mice entered the dark compartment within 10–60 s. The changes in PA performance are expressed as latency index [IL = (TL2–TL1)/TL1], which is calculated for each animal as the difference between retention and training latency times [19].

2.4 Acute and chronic treatments

During the acute treatment, the animals were allocated to the following drug treatment groups: PAM-2 [0.1, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mg/kg; by intraperitoneal (i.p.) injection] (n = 8–10), nicotine [0.05 mg/kg; by subcutaneous (s.c.) injection] (n = 8), scopolamine (1.0 mg/kg; i.p.) (n = 8), MLA (3.0 mg/kg; i.p.) (n = 8), DMXBA (0.3 and 1.0 mg/kg; i.p.) (n = 8), or vehicle (i.p.) (n = 8–10). Nicotine, scopolamine, and DMXBA were dissolved in saline solution (0.9% NaCl), whereas PAM-2 was suspended in 1% Tween 80 in saline solution (i.e., vehicle). The pH of the nicotine solution was adjusted to 7.0. The agents were administered at a volume of 10 ml/kg. Fresh drug solutions were prepared on each day of the experiment. Control groups received vehicle injections at the same volume and via the same route of administration.

The inactive doses of nicotine [19] and DMXBA [12] as well as the active doses of scopolamine [20], DMXBA [12], and MLA [21] were chosen based on previously published results. Each drug is administered separately, 60 min (PAM-2) or 30 min

(nicotine) before the memory acquisition/consolidation test or immediately after the memory consolidation test (i.e., nicotine, scopolamine, MLA, DMXBA, and PAM-2 alone). 24 h later (i.e., Day 2), PA tests were performed and the TL2 value was calculated. The dose and the pretreatment time selection for nicotine were based on our previous results, where it was demonstrated synergistic activity between an inactive dose of nicotine (0.05 mg/kg), after a pretreatment time of 30 min, with an inactive dose of imperatorin [19].

For the co-administration experiments, the animals were pretreated with PAM-2 30 min before the nicotine administration, and after additional 30 min, the memory acquisition/consolidation test was performed. In the case of memory consolidation, two different drug combinations were used immediately after the test: mice were first pretreated with PAM-2, and after 30 min the animals were treated with inactive doses of nicotine (0.05 mg/kg) or DMXBA (0.3 mg/kg). In additional experiments, animals were first pretreated with scopolamine or MLA, and after 30 min, treated with 1.0 mg/kg PAM-2.

To evaluate the long-lasting effect elicited by a single injection of PAM-2 (i.e., Day 1), the rodents were retested on Days 3, 8, or 15, expressed as TL3, TL8, or TL15, respectively.

For the chronic treatment, animals were injected with PAM-2 (0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mg/kg); or vehicle, once daily for 21 consecutive days. On the last day of treatment, PAM-2 or vehicle was injected immediately after the test and the rodents were retested 24 h later.

To evaluate any potential synergistic effect between PAM-2 and nAChR agonists on memory processes, PA tests were performed using inactive doses (i.e., doses that do not produce promnesic effects) of PAM-2 (0.1 or 0.5 mg/kg) with nicotine (0.05 mg/kg [19]), or DMXBA (0.3 mg/kg).

2.5 Locomotor activity and motor coordination

To determine the effect of PAM-2 on mouse locomotor activity, actimeter cages (32 cm in diameter, two light beams) (Multiserv, Lublin, Poland) kept in a sound-attenuated experimental room were used. Immediately after drug injection, each animal was placed in the actimeter cage. For the co-administration experiments, PAM-2 was injected 30 min before nicotine or DMXBA, or after scopolamine or MLA, and the animal placed in the actimeter cage. The number of crossings through the light beams by the mouse is recorded as the locomotor activity after 30 and 60 min.

To assess the ability of animals to maintain balance, the rota-rod test was used [22]. The animals that are able to stay on the rotating rod for 60 s are approved to conduct the described experiments.

2.6 Statistical analysis

To determine the statistical differences between various drugs and temporal regimens, the Prism software (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA) was used. Data were analyzed using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to compare the factors of PAM-2,

Fig. 1. The acute and chronic administration of PAM-2 improves memory acquisition/consolidation (A) and memory consolidation (B, C) in mice. For the acute treatment (A, B), appropriate groups of mice received injections (i.p.) of PAM-2 [0 (vehicle) (n = 10), 0.1 (n = 10), 0.5 (n = 10), 1.0 (n = 10), or 2.0 mg/kg (n = 10)] on Day 1, 60 min before the test (i.e., acquisition/consolidation) (A) or immediately after the test (i.e., consolidation) (B), and the rodents were retested 24 h (i.e., on Day 2). For the chronic treatment (C), mice were injected (i.p.) with PAM-2 [0 (vehicle) (n = 8), 0.5 (n = 8), 1.0 (n = 8), or 2.0 (n = 8) mg/kg] once daily during 21 consecutive days of treatment. Then, on the last day (i.e., Day 21), the PAM-2 and vehicle (i.e., control) groups were injected immediately after the PA test and the rodents retested 24 h later (i.e., on Day 22). Data represent the mean \pm SEM. The results from the Tukey's test analyses indicate: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$ vs. vehicle-treated mice group.

MLA or scopolamine pretreatment, and nicotine or DMXBA treatment. One-way ANOVA followed by the Tukey's post hoc test was used to compare the differences between each group as well as the differences between each day of treatment for each group. The confidence limit of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

2.7 Collection of tissues

Following the PA tests conducted after acute and repeated administration (i.e., 21 consecutive days) of PAM-2 (0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mg/kg), mice were decapitated, and the whole brain from each animal was carefully taken out and rinsed in isotonic saline solution to remove blood. The PFC and the hippocampus were rapidly dissected and frozen at -80°C .

2.8 Western blotting

To increase the protein yield, hippocampi collected from two animals of the same treatment group were pooled. Each cortical sample was prepared using an individual animal. A total number of six independent samples per tissue were used for each treatment group. Tissue samples were lysed in Cell Lysis Buffer containing 5 mM EDTA and 1 mM EGTA, supplemented with

1 mM sodium orthovanadate, 1 mM PMSF, and protease and phosphatase inhibitors (pH 7.5). The bicinchoninic acid assay was used to quantify the protein content from each lysate. Equivalent amount of proteins were then loaded on 4–12% pre cast polyacrylamide gels, separated by SDS-PAGE under reducing conditions, and transferred onto PVDF membranes. After blocking the membranes with 5% milk in Tris-buffered saline/0.1% Tween-20, the blots were incubated with the primary antibody of interest, followed by incubation with a horseradish peroxidase-conjugated secondary antibody. The immunoreactive protein bands were visualized by chemiluminescence (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, CA, USA), and quantified by volume densitometry (Fiji image processing package [23]) using β -actin or total-ERK1/2 as loading control.

3 Results

3.1 Effect of acute administration of PAM-2 on memory-related processes

The one-way ANOVA analyses of the results for the activity of PAM-2 on memory acquisition/consolidation (Fig. 1A) and memory consolidation (Fig. 1B) during the retention trial indicated that these effects are statistically significant [$F(3, 39) = 4.468, p = 0.0091$, and $F(4, 49) = 5.078, p = 0.0018$; respectively]. The post hoc Tukey's tests indicated that PAM-2 significantly increases the IL value for memory acquisition/consolidation after the acute administration of 1.0 mg/kg PAM-2 ($p < 0.05$), but not of 0.5 or 2.0 mg/kg, whereas for memory consolidation, PAM-2 significantly increases the IL value when compared to that for vehicle-treated mice at doses of 0.5 mg/kg ($p < 0.05$) as well as 1.0 and 2.0 mg/kg ($p < 0.01$).

3.2 Effect of chronic treatment with PAM-2 on memory-related processes

Fig. 1C shows the effect of PAM-2 (0.5, 1.0, or 2.0 mg/kg) on memory consolidation after 21 consecutive days of treatment. One-way ANOVA analyses indicate that chronically treated mice show statistically significant effects on memory consolidation [$F(3, 31) = 14.86, p < 0.0001$]. The post hoc Tukey's test revealed that the chronic treatment significantly increases the IL value ($p < 0.01$) at a dose of 1.0 mg/kg, but not at doses of 0.5 and 2.0 mg/kg, compared to that for the control group.

3.3 Long-term effects on memory-related processes elicited by a single injection of PAM-2 alone

The analysis of the results for the long-term activity elicited by a single injection of PAM-2 (all studied doses) on memory acquisition/consolidation and memory consolidation indicated statistically significant difference only on Day 3 [$F(3, 31) = 7.801, p = 0.0006$ (Fig. 2A), and $F(4, 39) = 3.809, p = 0.0113$ (Fig. 2B); respectively], but neither on Day 8 (data not shown) [$F(3, 31) = 1.780, p = 0.1738$ and $F(4, 39) = 2.204, p = 0.0886$; respectively], nor Day 15 (data not shown) [$F(3, 31) = 1.703, p = 0.1792$ and $F(4, 39) = 1.871, p = 0.1375$; respectively]. The post hoc Tukey's tests indicated that on Day 3, PAM-2 significantly increases the

Fig. 2. The acute injection of PAM-2 prolongs the improvement in memory acquisition/consolidation (A) and memory consolidation (B) in mice. Appropriate groups of mice received injections (i.p.) of PAM-2 [0 (vehicle) (n = 8), 0.1 (n = 8), 0.5 (n = 8), 1.0 (n = 8), or 2.0 mg/kg (n = 8)] on Day 1 immediately after the test (i.e., consolidation) or 60 min before the test (i.e., acquisition/consolidation), and the rodents were retested 48 h later (i.e., on Day 3). Data represent the mean \pm SEM. The results from the Tukey's test analyses indicate: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ vs vehicle-treated mice group.

IL value after the acute administration of 1.0 mg/kg PAM-2 [$p < 0.01$ for memory acquisition/consolidation (Fig. 2A) and $p < 0.05$ for memory consolidation (Fig. 2B)], but not of 0.5 or 2.0 mg/kg PAM-2.

Fig. 3. Effect of the acute administration of PAM-2 co-injected with nicotine on memory acquisition/consolidation (A) and memory consolidation (B) in mice. (A) For the evaluation of memory acquisition/consolidation, appropriate groups of mice were injected with 0.5 mg/kg PAM-2 alone (n = 8; i.p.), 0.05 mg/kg nicotine alone (n = 8; s.c.), or vehicle (n = 8, indicated as 0), 30 min before the PA test on Day 1. For the co-administration experiments, the animals were pretreated with 0.5 mg/kg PAM-2 (n = 8) 30 min before the nicotine administration, and after additional 30 min, the memory acquisition/consolidation test was performed. (B) For the evaluation of memory consolidation, 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2 alone (n = 8), 0.05 mg/kg nicotine alone (n = 8), vehicle (n = 8, indicated as 0), as well as 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2 co-administered with 0.05 mg/kg nicotine (n = 8), respectively, were injected immediately after the PA test on Day 1. The rodents were retested 24 h later (i.e., on Day 2). Data represent the mean \pm SEM.

3.4 Effect of nicotine alone or co-injected with PAM-2 on memory-related processes

The effects of nicotine (0.05 mg/kg) alone or co-injected with PAM-2 (0.1 and 0.5 mg/kg) on memory acquisition/consolidation (Fig. 3A) and consolidation (Fig. 3B) were determined during the retention trial of the PA task. In the case of memory acquisition/consolidation, the acute administration of inactive doses of nicotine (0.05 mg/kg) alone or combined with inactive doses of PAM-2 (0.5 mg/kg) did not change the IL values {two-way ANOVA: pretreatment [F(1, 28) = 0.00, $p = 0.9918$], treatment [F(1, 28) = 0.43, $p = 0.5167$], without ANOVA interaction effect [F(1, 28) = 1.66, $p = 0.2088$]}. Regarding memory consolidation, inactive doses of nicotine (0.05 mg/kg) alone or co-injected with an inactive dose of PAM-2 (0.1 mg/kg), respectively, did not change the IL values {two-way ANOVA: pretreatment [F(1, 28) = 0.01, $p = 0.9051$], treatment [F(1, 28) = 0.01, $p = 0.9433$], with ANOVA interaction effect [F(1, 28) = 0.82, $p = 0.3721$]}.

Regarding memory consolidation, inactive doses of nicotine (0.05 mg/kg) alone or co-injected with an inactive dose of PAM-2 (0.1 mg/kg), respectively, did not change the IL values {two-way ANOVA: pretreatment [F(1, 28) = 0.01, $p = 0.9051$], treatment [F(1, 28) = 0.01, $p = 0.9433$], with ANOVA interaction effect [F(1, 28) = 0.82, $p = 0.3721$]}.

3.5 Effect of methyllycaconitine on the promnesic activity elicited by PAM-2

The effect of 3.0 mg/kg MLA, a selective $\alpha 7$ -antagonist, on memory consolidation elicited by 1.0 mg/kg PAM-2 was studied by comparing the activity of PAM-2 in the absence and presence of MLA (Fig. 4A). The two-way ANOVA analysis revealed statistically significant effects {pretreatment [F(1, 28) = 8.64, $p = 0.0065$], treatment [F(1, 28) = 4.58, $p = 0.0413$], ANOVA interaction effect [F(1, 28) = 10.37, $p = 0.0032$]}. The post hoc Tukey's test indicated that MLA decreases the IL value observed for PAM-2 ($p < 0.001$, Fig. 4A).

Fig. 4. Effects on memory consolidation in mice mediated by acute administration of PAM-2 co-injected with methyllycaconitine (MLA) (A) or scopolamine (B). Appropriate groups of mice received 1.0 mg/kg PAM-2 alone (n = 8), 1.0 mg/kg scopolamine alone (n = 8), 3.0 mg/kg MLA alone (n = 8), or vehicle (n = 8, indicated as 0). For the co-administration experiments, the animals were pretreated with 3.0 mg/kg MLA (n = 8) or 1.0 mg/kg scopolamine (n = 8) 30 min before the PAM-2 administration [1.0 mg/kg (n = 8)] after the PA test on Day 1. The rodents were retested 24 h later (i.e., on Day 2). Data represent the mean \pm SEM. The results from the Tukey's test analyses indicate: * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$ vs vehicle-treated mice group, ### $p < 0.001$ vs scopolamine-treated mice, and && $p < 0.01$ vs 1.0 mg/kg PAM-2-treated mice.

Fig. 5. Effects elicited by PAM-2 and DMXBA treatments on memory consolidation in mice. On Day 1, animals were injected (i.p.) immediately after the PA test with 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2 alone (n = 8), 0.3 mg/kg DMXBA alone (n = 8), or vehicle (n = 8, indicated as 0), as well as with 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2 co-administered with 0.3 mg/kg DMXBA (n = 8). The rodents were retested 24 h later (i.e., on Day 2) (A) or 48 h later (i.e., on Day 3) to evaluate the prolonged effects elicited by 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2 co-injected with 0.3 mg/kg DMXBA (B). Data represent the mean \pm SEM. The results from the Tukey's test analyses indicate: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ vs. 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2-treated mice.

3.6 Effect of PAM-2 on scopolamine-induced memory impairment

The two-way ANOVA analysis of the results for the activity of PAM-2 (1.0 mg/kg) on memory impairment elicited by 1.0 mg/kg scopolamine (Fig. 4B), shows that pretreatment [$F(1,28) = 1.67, p = 0.02048$] and treatment [$F(1,28) = 28.54, p < 0.001$] effects are statistically significant. However, there is no statistically significant ANOVA interaction effect [$F(1, 28) = 2.35, p = 0.3320$], indicating that the promnesic activity of PAM-2 is not affected by this muscarinic antagonist. To elucidate the meaning of the pretreatment or treatment effects, the post hoc Tukey's test was used next. The results indicated a significant decrease in the IL value for the scopolamine-treated group compared to vehicle-treated mice ($p < 0.05$), in agreement with literature data [20]. These results reveal that PAM-2 recovers mice from the memory deficits induced by scopolamine ($p < 0.001$) (Fig. 4B) to comparable values elicited by PAM-2 alone.

3.7 Effect of PAM-2 alone or co-injected with DMXBA on memory consolidation

The one-way ANOVA analyses of the results for the activity of DMXBA (0.3 and 1.0 mg/kg) and 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2 on memory consolidation (Fig. 5A) indicated statistically significant differences [$F(3, 31) = 5.057, p = 0.0063$]. However, the post hoc Tukey's test indicated that only 1.0 mg/kg DMXBA ($p < 0.05$) enhances memory consolidation compared to the control group (data not shown). Both 0.3 mg/kg DMXBA and 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2 were found to be inactive doses ($p > 0.05$). To determine whether the co-administration of inactive doses of

DMXBA (0.3 mg/kg) and of PAM-2 (0.1 mg/kg) produce promnesic activity, the effect of both drugs on memory consolidation was determined during the retention trial of the PA task (Fig. 5A). The two-way ANOVA analysis revealed statistically significant differences in the treatment [$F(1, 28) = 9.95, p = 0.0038$], but neither in the pretreatment [$F(1, 28) = 0.93, p = 0.3420$] nor ANOVA interaction [$F(1, 28) = 1.35, p = 0.2549$] effects.

To elucidate the meaning of the treatment effect, the post hoc Tukey's test was used. The results demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the combination of 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2 and 0.3 mg/kg DMXBA compared to that for PAM-2 alone ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 5A).

3.8 Long-term effects on memory consolidation elicited by a single injection of PAM-2 alone or co-administrated with DMXBA

The two-way ANOVA analysis revealed that a single injection of PAM-2 co-administered with DMXBA prolongs the effect on memory consolidation until Day 3 {pretreatment [$F(1, 28) = 0.96, p = 0.3345$], treatment [$F(1, 28) = 7.75, p = 0.0095$], without ANOVA interaction effect [$F(1, 28) = 2.70, p = 0.1115$]}. To elucidate the meaning of the treatment effect, the post hoc Tukey's test was used. The results demonstrated that the co-administration of DMXBA (0.3 mg/kg) with an inactive dose of PAM-2 (0.1 mg/kg) increases the IL value compared to that for 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2 alone on Day 3 ($p < 0.01$) (Fig. 5B).

3.9 Effect of used drugs on locomotor activity and motor coordination

Animals injected with PAM-2 at doses of 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, or 2.0 mg/kg, show no impact on motor coordination using the rota-rod test (data not shown).

Table 1 shows the locomotor activity results (30 and 60 min) after the acute administration of PAM-2 (0.1, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mg/kg), nicotine (0.05 mg/kg), scopolamine (1.0 mg/kg), DMXBA (0.3 mg/kg), MLA (3.0 mg/kg), compared to that for the vehicle. The same table shows the results for the drug combination experiments, including those for the co-injection of inactive doses of PAM-2 (0.5 or 0.1 mg/kg) and inactive doses of nicotine (0.05 mg/kg) or DMXBA (0.3 mg/kg), as well as the results for active doses of PAM-2 (1.0 mg/kg) with scopolamine (1.0 mg/kg) or MLA (3.0 mg/kg).

Two-way ANOVA analyses evaluated for each group are included in Table 1. There is no statistically significant difference after co-injections of PAM-2 (0.1, 0.5 and 1.0 mg/kg) with 0.3 mg/kg DMXBA, 0.05 mg/kg nicotine, or 3.0 mg/kg MLA. Our results indicate that the acute administration of PAM-2, at the used doses, did not affect the locomotor activity of mice compared to respective control groups. This is in agreement with previous data indicating that 1.0 mg/kg PAM-2 does not produce unspecific locomotor activity after acute and chronic (3 weeks) treatments, and after drug cessation (2 weeks) [9]. As expected, scopolamine significantly increases locomotor activity in agreement with literature [20] (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of different combinations of drugs on spontaneous locomotor activity in mice.

Time (min)	Type of treatment				Statistical analysis
	Vehicle	0.05 mg/kg Nicotine	0.5 mg/kg PAM-2	0.5 mg/kg PAM-2 + 0.05 mg/kg Nicotine	F, p
30	358 ± 45	349 ± 49	325 ± 29	278 ± 57	Pretreatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.17$; $p = 0.2702$ Treatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.36$; $p = 0.5542$ ANOVA interactions: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.17$; $p = 0.6863$
60	618 ± 49	645 ± 73	459 ± 67	396 ± 51	Pretreatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 11.19$; $p = 0.024$ Treatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.08$; $p = 0.7730$ ANOVA interactions: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.54$; $p = 0.4698$
	Vehicle	0.3 mg/kg DMXBA	0.1 mg/kg PAM-2	0.3 mg/kg DMXBA + 0.1 mg/kg PAM-2	F, p
30	323 ± 30	351 ± 34	328 ± 25	354 ± 56	Pretreatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.01$; $p = 0.9227$ Treatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.48$; $p = 0.4928$ ANOVA interactions: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.00$; $p = 0.9742$
60	468 ± 86	522 ± 43	536 ± 41	519 ± 70	Pretreatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.21$; $p = 0.6045$ Treatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.09$; $p = 0.7641$ ANOVA interactions: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.32$; $p = 0.5733$
	Vehicle	1.0 mg/kg Scopolamine	1.0 mg/kg PAM-2	1.0 mg/kg PAM-2 + 1.0 mg/kg Scopolamine	F, p
30	343 ± 28	791 ± 111	387 ± 41	915 ± 22	Pretreatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 61.61$; $p < 0.0001$ Treatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 1.78$; $p = 0.1923$ ANOVA interactions: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.39$; $p = 0.5352$
60	601 ± 62	1615 ± 129	540 ± 60	1698 ± 111	Pretreatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 128.62$; $p < 0.0001$ Treatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.01$; $p = 0.9078$ ANOVA interactions: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.57$; $p = 0.4580$
	Vehicle	3.0 mg/kg MLA	1.0 mg/kg PAM-2	1.0 mg/kg PAM-2 + 3.0 mg/kg MLA	F, p
30	301 ± 28	447 ± 49	415 ± 49	354 ± 38	Pretreatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 2.08$; $p = 0.1604$ Treatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.03$; $p = 0.8638$ ANOVA interactions: $F_{(1,28)} = 1.64$; $p = 0.2108$
60	437 ± 89	491 ± 76	681 ± 99	552 ± 65	Pretreatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 3.33$; $p = 0.0786$ Treatment: $F_{(1,28)} = 0.20$; $p = 0.6585$ ANOVA interactions: $F_{(1,28)} = 1.22$; $p = 0.2787$

The locomotor activity (number of interruptions of light beams) was recorded 30 and 60 min immediately after drug injections. Each group consists of 8 animals. Data are presented as the mean ± SEM.

Fig. 6. Different doses of PAM-2 (0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 mg/kg) do not change the expression of $\alpha 7$ nAChRs in the (A, C) hippocampus and (B, D) prefrontal cortex. Mice were treated with different doses of PAM-2 acutely (A, B) or chronically (i.e., for 21 consecutive days) (C, D) as described in Section 2. The respective hippocampi and cortices from different animal groups were lysed, its proteins separated by SDS-PAGE, and subsequently blotted using high specificity antibodies raised against the murine/rat $\alpha 7$ nAChR. Representative blots (upper panels) are compared to that for β -actin (loading control). The densitometric quantification of the $\alpha 7$ nAChR content is shown in the lower panels ($n = 6$). The one-way ANOVA results from the Tukey's post-hoc test indicate lack of statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) vs vehicle (control, indicated as 0).

3.10 Effect of PAM-2 on the expression of $\alpha 7$ nAChRs in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex

The influence of PAM-2 on the expression of $\alpha 7$ nAChRs in the hippocampus and PFC was determined in mice injected with PAM-2 (0.5, 1.0, or 2.0 mg/kg) after acute (Fig. 6A,B) and chronic (i.e., 21 days) (Fig. 6C,D) treatments, respectively, by using the western blotting technique. Previous studies have confirmed that this technique is sensitive enough to determine changes in $\alpha 7$ nAChR expression [24,25]. To overcome the potential lack of antibody specificity [26], an antibody that has been extensively validated for $\alpha 7$ nAChR studies [27] was selected to determine $\alpha 7$ subunit expression. The one-way ANOVA analysis revealed that neither acute (Fig. 6A,B) nor chronic (Fig. 6C,D) treatments up-regulate $\alpha 7$ nAChRs in the hippocampus [acute: $F(2, 15) = 0.698, p = 0.513$; chronic: $F(3, 20) = 0.039, p = 0.990$], and PFC [acute: $F(2, 15) = 0.413, p = 0.669$; chronic $F(3, 20) = 1.237, p = 0.323$].

3.11 Effect of PAM-2 on ERK1/2 phosphorylation in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex

The influence of PAM-2 on ERK1/2 phosphorylation was determined in the hippocampus and PFC of mice injected with

0.5, 1.0, or 2.0 mg/kg PAM-2 after acute (Fig. 7A,B) and chronic (Fig. 7C,D) treatments, respectively. The one-way ANOVA analysis revealed that the acute and chronic treatments modulate ERK1/2 phosphorylation in the hippocampus [acute: $F(2, 15) = 23.77, p < 0.001$; chronic: $F(3, 20) = 11.65, p = 0.001$] and PFC [acute: $F(2, 15) = 25.18, p < 0.001$; chronic: $F(3, 20) = 15.23, p < 0.001$] in a statistically significant manner (Fig. 7B). The post hoc Tukey's test indicated that the acute treatment with PAM-2 (0.5 and 1.0 mg/kg) decreases ERK1/2 phosphorylation in both hippocampus (Fig. 7A) and PFC (Fig. 7B) ($p < 0.001$). Opposite to that, the chronic treatment with 0.5 mg/kg PAM-2 ($p < 0.01$), but not with 1.0 and 2.0 mg/kg ($p > 0.05$), increases ERK1/2 phosphorylation in the hippocampus (Fig. 7C), whereas doses of 0.5 and 1.0 mg/kg PAM-2 (at least $p < 0.05$), but not of 2.0 mg/kg ($p > 0.05$), increase ERK1/2 phosphorylation in the PFC (Fig. 7D).

4 Discussion

Our PA results indicate that the acute administration of PAM-2 alone improves memory-related processes. However, a clear discrimination between the effects elicited by PAM-2 during the acquisition and consolidation processes is difficult. More specifically, when the drug is administered before the PA test (on Day 1), some concentration of the drug is still present in the brain, consequently, the influence of PAM-2 on the early stages

Fig. 7. Effect of PAM-2 on ERK1/2 phosphorylation in the (A, C) hippocampus and (B, D) prefrontal cortex, respectively. Hippocampi and cortices were first obtained from mice treated acutely (A, B) or chronically (i.e., for 21 consecutive days) (C, D) as described in Section 2. The respective lysates were subsequently immunoblotted for ERK1/2 and their phosphorylated forms. Six independent samples per treatment group for each tissue were assessed. Representative blots (upper panels) and relative changes in ERK1/2 phosphorylation, measured by volume densitometry (lower panels) ($n = 6$) are depicted. The one-way ANOVA results from the Tukey's post-hoc test indicate: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ vs vehicle (control, indicated as 0).

of memory consolidation cannot be excluded. Since acquisition cannot be tested independently, the observed PAM-2 effect is considered as the acquisition/consolidation effect.

The memory improvements elicited by PAM-2 persisted for up to 48 h, contrary to that for DMXBA alone that persisted for up to 24 h. The simplest explanation of our results is that PAM-2 enhances the agonistic activity of the endogenous neurotransmitters ACh and/or choline on $\alpha 7$ nAChRs. The evidence indicating that the selective $\alpha 7$ -antagonist MLA inhibits the promnesic activity elicited by PAM-2 supports the view that the observed PAM-2 activity is in fact mediated by $\alpha 7$ nAChRs. Our results support previous animal studies reporting that different $\alpha 7$ PAMs [12,28–30] improve distinct types of memory processes as well as sensory gating, which is disabled in schizophrenics (reviewed in Refs. [3,6,7,29]). The results from the chronic treatment indicate for the first time that 1.0 mg/kg PAM-2 enhances memory consolidation, with comparable outcome as that for the acute treatment.

Our findings indicate that the combination of inactive doses of both PAM-2 and nicotine does not enhance memory processes. This result might be related to the fact that nicotine is a non-selective agonist and may stimulate (and desensitize) other nAChR subtypes, thus producing additional effects that mask the activity elicited by PAM-2 through $\alpha 7$ nAChRs. On the contrary, the combination of inactive doses of both PAM-2 and DMXBA (an $\alpha 7$ selective agonist) improves memory processes when compared to PAM-2 alone. A similar result was observed using two different behavioral tests to study cognitive flexibility [12]. This effect could be explained by the potentiating activity of PAM-2 on DMXBA-activated $\alpha 7$ nAChRs. DMXBA (1.0 mg/kg) per se presents promnesic and procognitive activity [31] and facilitates long-term potentiation (LTP) as shown in rat hippocampal slices [32]. In addition, the activity elicited by different agonists can be enhanced by distinct PAMs [33]. Based on these and other studies, it has been postulated that $\alpha 7$ nAChRs expressed in the hippocampus and PFC play an important role in memory acquisition, LTM, and LTP [2,34–36]. The observed memory improvement after long-term use of PAM-2 alone or combined with DMXBA may be related to the process of LTP in the hippocampus by enhancing neurotransmitter- or agonist-activated $\alpha 7$ nAChRs, respectively. Further studies need to be performed to determine whether PAM-2 increases LTP in the hippocampus.

To determine the neuronal mechanisms involved in the promnesic activity of PAM-2, the expression of $\alpha 7$ nAChRs in the hippocampus and PFC was studied by western blotting. Our results indicate that the expression of $\alpha 7$ nAChRs in these two brain areas changes neither after acute nor chronic PAM-2 treatment. This is consistent with previous results supporting the view that $\alpha 7$ nAChRs are up-regulated by agonists but not by PAMs [5,13]. Since PAM-2 has procognitive [12] and promnesic activity (this work), this evidence does not support the hypothesis that $\alpha 7$ nAChR up-regulation is necessary to achieve procognitive/promnesic activity as stated previously [13].

We also focused on intracellular signaling pathways, more specifically on ERK1/2 phosphorylation. ERK1/2 is a kinase involved in the consolidation of spatial memory and necessary for LTM in the hippocampus [37], its overexpression contributes to memory enhancement [14], and it is activated in the medial

PFC (mPFC) after learning activity [16]. Our results showed that the chronic treatment with PAM-2 (0.5 and 1.0 mg/kg) increases ERK1/2 phosphorylation in the hippocampus and PFC, whereas the acute treatment decreases ERK1/2 phosphorylation. This is the first time that a selective $\alpha 7$ -PAM (i.e., PAM-2) shows a differential effect on ERK1/2 phosphorylation depending on the length of treatment. The mechanism underlying this dual effect is not clear. A potential explanation is that other signaling factors (e.g., protein kinase A and Ca^{2+} -calmodulin-dependent protein kinase; reviewed by Lee [39]) might instead be involved in the promnesic activity observed after acute PAM-2 treatment, with a subsequent decrease in ERK1/2 phosphorylation. On the other hand, the promnesic activity observed after chronic PAM-2 treatment could be related to the increased ERK1/2 phosphorylation. It has been shown that activation of the ERK cascade is required for LTM, but not short-term memory, in invertebrates [38]. and vertebrates [37], and that ERK1/2 phosphorylation in the hippocampus as well as mPFC is required for LTM [15]. Based on this previous evidence, it is tempting to speculate that ERK1/2 phosphorylation is relevant for the formation of LTM, and that ERK1/2 phosphorylation may accumulate over time upon chronic PAM-2 treatment. Interestingly, the behavior observed for PAM-2 is opposite to that determined for the selective $\alpha 7$ nAChR agonist A-582941, which induces ERK2 phosphorylation in the PFC after acute, but not chronic, administration [13]. A potential explanation is that the chronic treatment with an agonist desensitizes the $\alpha 7$ nAChR, diminishing the ERK1/2 phosphorylation triggered by $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation, whereas PAM-2, a putative type II PAM, may actually reactivate desensitized $\alpha 7$ nAChRs [9], potentially maintaining ERK1/2 phosphorylation after several days of treatment.

We further demonstrated that the acute treatment with PAM-2 reverses the memory impairment elicited by scopolamine, with no effect by this muscarinic antagonist on the promnesic activity of PAM-2. Previous results indicate that $\alpha 7$ -selective PAMs improve acquisition memory (i.e., NS1738), attention (i.e., PNU-120596), pre-attention tasks (i.e., SB-206553), and object recognition (i.e., PAM-2) in animals treated with drugs that induce cognitive deficits [12,28,29,40]. In this regard, $\alpha 7$ PAMs may be useful in conditions of altered cholinergic tone (e.g., AD), and/or of cognitive function impairments (e.g., reduced cognitive ability induced by strokes, AD, and schizophrenia).

5 Conclusions

Our results indicate that PAM-2 (1) produces promnesic activity mediated by $\alpha 7$ nAChRs, (2) enhances the promnesic activity elicited by $\alpha 7$ -selective agonists, (3) recovers animals from scopolamine-induced memory deficits, and (4) increases ERK1/2 phosphorylation in hippocampus and PFC only after chronic treatment. PAM-2 may constitute a promising therapeutic agent for the treatment of memory impairment in neurological conditions such as AD and schizophrenia where the cholinergic tone is altered. The combination of beneficial activities elicited by PAM-2, including promnesic (this work), procognitive [12], and antidepressant-like [9,10] activity, could be clinically relevant for the treatment of AD patients where cognitive impairment is often linked with depression, which correspond to ~40% of the AD population [41].

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by grants from the TEAM research subsidy from the Foundation for Polish Science, Poland (to K.J.), from the National Science Center, Poland (SONATA funding, UMO-2013/09/D/NZ7/04549) [to K.T-D. (PI) and H.R.A. (Co-PI)], and by a Polpharma Scientific Foundation scholarship (to A.W.).

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